

THE ROLE OF PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATION IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CONTINUOUS EDUCATION

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Annotation: Improving the quality and efficiency of the education system in the country, the formation of modern knowledge and skills of preschoolers, close cooperation and integration between the education system and science, the integration of education and systematic work to ensure continuity.

Keywords: development, education, cooperation, national education.

Looking back at history, the great Greek scientist Aristotle said, "The fate of the country is decided by the education of the youth." See, these thoughts were spoken before Christ. Therefore, the issue of education and upbringing has always been gaining urgent importance since the time when humanity began to live a conscious life. The role and importance of the preschool education system in the life of our society cannot be measured by anything. It is the attention to the field of preschool education that will create a solid foundation for the future development of the country.

Preschool education is to educate children intellectually and morally on the basis of the nation's rich national cultural-historical heritage and universal values. To form children's feelings of national pride and patriotism, to form preschool children's need for education and desire to study, to encourage them regularly provides preparation for the educational process, development of children's thinking. Because of this, a new ministry was established. The new ministry is tasked with developing and implementing a unified state policy in the field of preschool education, expanding the network of state and non-state preschool educational institutions, strengthening the material and technical base, providing them with qualified pedagogic personnel, including children in preschool educational institutions. the task of dramatically increasing children's education, implementing modern educational programs and technologies into educational processes, and radically improving the quality of children's preparation for school.¹

Today, the state program on expanding the network of preschool educational organizations, strengthening their material and technical base, and building new kindergartens is being adopted and implemented. Taking into account the experience of developed countries, great importance is attached to expanding the network of non-state educational institutions, including non-state kindergartens. This serves to create healthy competition in the system and increase the type of educational services. Special attention was paid to the training of personnel specialized in the field of preschool education. Developing advanced pedagogical methods and methods that meet modern requirements, creating and publishing a new generation of educational and educational methodical literature is also an extremely urgent task in this field. A plan of measures for the implementation of the tasks set in the 2017-2021 program for the further improvement of the preschool education system was developed. The

¹Prezidentimizning "Maktabgacha ta'lim vazirligi boshqaruvini tubdan takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"dagi farmoni. 2019- yil 30-sentyabr

task of preschool education is to educate children in terms of the nation's rich national, cultural-historical heritage and spiritual and moral values, to form children's feelings of national patriotism, to form preschool children's need for education, and to prepare them for the educational process on a regular basis. , development of children's thinking, formation of skills of independent and free expression of one's opinion, ensuring children's physical and mental health.

Preschool education and training is a type of education aimed at teaching and educating children, developing them intellectually, spiritually, morally, maturely, aesthetically and physically, as well as preparing children for general secondary education. Preschool education and upbringing also includes one-year compulsory preparation of children aged six to seven years for primary education. It implies the creation of socio-political, legal, psychological-pedagogical and other conditions for the conscious selection of an educational and professional program and subsequent thorough mastering, and the education of educators who feel their responsibility to society, the state and the family.

Forms of cooperation with parents in a preschool educational institution are important to ensure all-round development of the child. The evidence presented above shows that forming parents' perceptions of the positive aspects of preschool education in the formation of a child's personality is one of the most urgent issues. it is necessary to develop, develop, create and put into practice.

Forming parents' ideas about the positive aspects of preschool education in the formation of a child's personality, increasing the effectiveness of the educational process and putting it into practice is one of the urgent tasks of today. In fact, educational reforms greatly helped to reveal a certain level of intellectual potential of a person and to find his place in society. Therefore, in the principles of the state requirements for the development of primary and preschool children of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the role of adults in the education and development of children is defined as the main and important role. It can be seen that the cooperation of adults, especially parents and educators, is very important for the child's healthy development in all aspects.

Observations show that, among some shortcomings, the cooperation of parents of preschool children is not at the required level. The reason for this is the lack of educational tools and conditions for education in preschool educational organizations, and secondly, the lack of knowledge of pedagogues in organizing activities with parents. According to the concept of development of the preschool education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, the tasks of eliminating problems in the field and providing high-quality preparation for school education of preschool children are envisaged. For this reason, we chose the topic "Formation of positive aspects of preschool education in the formation of children's personality by parents". In the action strategy for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "Expanding the network of preschool educational institutions and fundamentally improving the conditions for all-round intellectual, aesthetic and physical development of children in these institutions, seriously increasing the inclusion of children in preschool education and providing access opportunities, raising the level of qualifications of pedagogues and specialists" are defined as important tasks. This, in turn, involves instilling modern approaches into the integrated content of the preschool education system, determining the pedagogical and psychological directions of ensuring children's thinking activity, clarifying

the methodological possibilities of developing children's thinking activity during preschool education, developing children's thinking activity requires the development of a model of a directed pedagogical process based on priority principles and ensuring mutual cooperation between the preschool education organization and the family. Today, the attitude of parents towards the organization of preschool education remains negative.

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